

The Role of Financial Intelligence in Enhancing Performance Efficiency of Private Iraqi Banks: A Case Study Bank of Baghdad

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Online Publication: 07 August 2025	Important it highlights a vital issue that impacts performance efficiency in Iraqi private banks. In light of financial and economic challenges, some banks, including the Bank of Baghdad, have adopted a new, realistic, and usable tool to evaluate and improve performance efficiency. This tool uses financial intelligence as an advanced method for analysing data, making accurate strategic decisions, achieving sustainable performance, and reducing risks surrounding banking activities. Essence of Problem can be expressed through following questions: What is level of financial intelligence prevailing within Bank of Baghdad? To what extent does financial intelligence contribute to improving financial performance efficiency indicators at Bank of Baghdad? Aims to measure impact of financial intelligence on improving financial performance efficiency indicators and to determine the relationship between financial intelligence and financial performance it also analyses the level of financial intelligence at the Bank of Baghdad as an example of Iraqi private banks. Study Hypotheses is based on a main hypothesis: "There is a significant relationship between financial intelligence and improving financial performance efficiency of Bank of Baghdad." Results Financial intelligence enhances the efficiency of the Bank of Baghdad's financial performance. This was achieved in 2023, as the financial intelligence ratio reached 3.88 this positively impacted the financial performance efficiency index for 2023, reaching 4.48.
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KEYWORDS: Financial Intelligence, Performance Efficiency, Bank of Baghdad (BBOB)	
JEL: G53, G21, L25, M41	

1. INTRODUCTION

Economic, financial, and technological changes are accelerating globally, requiring new developments and modern tools to enhance performance efficiency. In this context, the need for cognitive and strategic tools capable of supporting sound decision-making and enhancing performance quality is evident. Financial intelligence is among these tools, which has become a necessary requirement for financial institutions, given its ability to understand and analyse financial data, particularly in the banking sector. Iraqi private banks face multiple challenges related to low levels of efficiency, weak risk management capabilities, and fluctuating financial performance indicators, amid a complex local environment and a highly competitive

banking market. Bank of Baghdad is a real-life example of this environment, making it an appropriate case for studying the extent to which financial intelligence contributes to improving performance efficiency.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Framework for Financial Intelligence: -

Financial intelligence is one aspect of measuring financial knowledge intelligence. It expresses the ability of an individual or institution to solve financial problems and determine their position on improving financial knowledge in order to demonstrate good financial behaviour. It is necessary to have sufficient financial knowledge that influences the direction of financial

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management, which in turn affects investment and financing decisions. There must also be a degree of intelligence to be able to manage money and how to keep it, and thus good financial and investment behaviour. (Al-Awadly & Washwasha, 2023). It is a measure of the degree of understanding of key financial concepts and the ability and confidence to manage personal financial decisions by making appropriate short-term decisions and sound long-term financial planning, taking into account life events and changing economic conditions (Omorieg, 2019). Financial intelligence is defined as ability to solve financial problems and interpret and evaluate financial data to make a better financial decision and position. He pointed out that financial intelligence is the bank's ability to organize and manage its financial affairs, and the ability to earn money, manage it and

manage assets so that they can be multiplied to the maximum extent in the shortest period of time, and preserve these assets. Financial intelligence aims to achieve financial freedom, which is one of the elements that must be achieved in financial prosperity (Mohd & Kamaruddin, 2016). Financial intelligence is often used in organizations and refers to the knowledge and skills needed to understand financial and accounting principles applied in the business world. Financial intelligence means having the competence and knowledge of best practices needed to achieve specific goals. Financial intelligence can allow an individual or a family to properly manage their finances, plan, maximize the value of their time, and most importantly, reap economic benefits (Miečinskienė, Jurevičienė, & Gudelytė, 2023). The figure below shows financial intelligence

Figure1. Illustration Financial Intelligence

Source: Prepared by researchers based on literature

2.2. Importance of Financial Intelligence is highlighted by following:

- Adding strategic value to the bank and protecting its assets. It also enhances sound decision-making by relying on reliable financial information, which leads to increased competitiveness and operational effectiveness.
- Maximizing data accuracy, enabling deeper analysis of financial data and the likelihood of future events, thereby reducing uncertainty.
- Identifying various irregularities in financial transactions, including money laundering, tax evasion, intentional misrepresentation of funds, and other violations of accounting rules (Safi, S. K., 2024).
- Reducing costs, improving service quality, enhancing efficiency, controlling risks, and mitigating the challenges facing banks.
- Having financial intelligence is essential for financial health. It helps in dealing with financial problems, reading financial reports, and choosing

sound investments. These skills lead to financial success over time (Li, 2024).

- Developing and enhancing financial intelligence for banks helps achieve financial automation for these banks, while simultaneously achieving integrated business and financial management (Mu, 2020).

2.3. Financial Intelligence Skills are Classified as follows:

- ❖ Market intelligence skills which enable decision makers to acquire assets at the lowest cost. The American Institute of Financial Analysts classifies these skills into three levels, including: academic skills, professional skills, and technical skills (Al-Rawazeq, Kazem, & Al-Amri, 2020).
- ❖ Administrative methods, which are the methods employed by financial management directly related to financial assets, helping to increase investor desire to purchase a portion of those assets. These methods include the following: (Abboud & Abbas, 2023).
 - Pricing Methods: These include determining the optimal price for the product and maximizing profits under competitive conditions.

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- Accounts Receivable and payable management methods: These include accurately balancing accounts.
- Cash methods: Obtaining cash at the appropriate time, especially when defaults are high.
- Employment Methods: These include coordinating the number of employees and working hours, while balancing employee satisfaction within established systems and skill levels, on the one hand, and time management at the lowest cost, on the other.
- Accounting Recording Methods: Recording accounting transactions has become more complex as accounting has become more technologically advanced. This requires more sophisticated methods, including smart programs that record and analyse all financial transactions in real time, as well as manipulation permitted by accounting standards, known as creative accounting (Kinza & Amina, 2022)

2.4. Concept of Financial Performance Efficiency in

Banks: Performance is defined as the efficiency, effectiveness and value creation for stakeholders. Therefore, performance from a financial point of view is an assessment of the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization's use of financial implementation standards. It is one of the basic methods for evaluating and ensuring the financial soundness of the organization based on examining its financial ratios in the organization's performance (Abdelraheem, 2024). From the definition, we conclude that performance is a measure of efficiency and effectiveness. As for good or profitable financial performance, it is an analysis to evaluate the bank's ability to achieve profit or gains in a specific period of time. It is a measure to evaluate the level of efficiency and effectiveness of the bank's management, which appears in the profits resulting from revenues or investment income (Yuniawati & Farman, 2023).

2.5. Financial Performance Objectives are as follows:

- **Achieving Financial Liquidity:** Liquidity undoubtedly reflects a bank's ability to quickly convert assets into cash to meet short-term obligations. Liquidity also addresses liquidity shortages, which could negatively impact the bank's development, its ability to exploit investment opportunities, and its ability to fulfil its obligations to customers, suppliers, and other parties (Al-Shammari, 2022).
- **Enhancing Profitability and Return:** as profitability reflects the efficiency of the bank's

management in generating profits from its core activities, as well as its ability to generate net profits that enhance its financial sustainability.

- **Value Generation:** which involves achieving future returns commensurate with the risks associated with current investments and outperforming the returns of alternative investments with similar risks (Brizat, 2022)
- **Performance Monitoring and Evaluation:** where the bank's activity and financial and economic conditions are monitored to determine the impact of financial performance on profitability and liquidity, as well as to identify strengths and weaknesses and develop plans to improve performance. This helps investors understand the institution's financial position by providing accurate information that helps them compare and analyse financial data to make investment decisions (Imran, 2022).
- **Improving Financial Performance:** to avoid crises that could negatively impact competitiveness and financial stability, by protecting the bank from long-term crises and ensuring its continuity by providing financial stability that enables it to adapt to local and external economic and financial challenges.
- **Supporting Sustainability:** and survival by achieving continuity and growth through improved efficiency and effectiveness, contributing to improved relationships with customers and suppliers, and enhancing investor confidence (Al-Qahri, 2017)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Model: This research has two variables, as follows:

- Independent Variable: Financial Intelligence
- Dependent Variable: Performance Efficiency

3.2. Descriptive analysis: - Bank of Baghdad ¹(BBOB) was established as a private joint-stock company in Iraq in 1992, becoming the first licensed private bank in the country following the amendment of the Central Bank of Iraq Law. Its fully paid-up capital amounts to 300 billion Iraqi dinars, which were later increased through the issuance of 50 billion free shares. The bank's beginnings date back to a capital of 100 million Iraqi dinars, and in 2004, its shares were listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange. The bank's activities gradually expanded, initially limited to commercial banking until 1998, before it commenced full-fledged banking activities after receiving official approval from the Central Bank of Iraq. Bank of Baghdad's primary objective is to provide effective financial solutions that support the success of

¹ Abbreviation for Bank of Baghdad

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its clients, both locally and internationally. And The table below shows general information about the bank

Table1. Illustration General Information of Bank of Baghdad(BBOB)

Bank Name	Year of Establishment	Initial Capital ² (IQD)	Stock Symbol	Type	Service Area	Number of Branches
Bank of Baghdad	1992	100,000,000	BBOB	Commercial Financial Institution	-Iraq -Lebanon	35

Source: Prepared by researchers based on bank data

3.3. Financial Intelligence Indicators: - We will calculate financial intelligence indicators using table as follows: (Ohelal, 2017).

Table2. Illustration Financial Intelligence Indicators

Item	Equation
Financial Intelligence value production	$= (\text{Value Production} + \text{Money Production}) \times (\text{Control, Regulation, and Planned Net Income})$ $\text{Value Creation} = \text{Market Value Added} - \text{Invested Capital}$ $\text{Market value} = \text{share price} \times \text{paid-in capital}$ $\text{Invested capital} = \text{book value} \times \text{paid-in capital}$
Money production	Money production = net profit
Control	$\text{Capital adequacy ratio} = \frac{\text{capital}}{\text{total assets}}$ $\text{Profitability ratio} = \frac{\text{Net profit}}{\text{Total assets}}$ $\text{Credit risk ratio} = \frac{\text{Allowance for doubtful debts}}{\text{Total credit granted}}$ $\text{Liquidity ratio} = \frac{\text{cash assets}}{\text{total assets}}$
Organization	Organization ratio = number of employees who attended training courses / total bank employees
Planning	$\text{Planned Net Income} = \text{Planned Gross Income} - \text{Income Tax}$ $\text{Planned Gross Income} = \text{Planned Revenue} - \text{Planned Expenses}$

Source: Prepared by researchers based on (Ohelal, 2017).

Now, researchers will calculate financial intelligence indicators of Bank of Baghdad (BBOB) for period from 2011 to 2023, for eleven years.

Table3. Illustration Financial Intelligence Indicators of Bank of Baghdad for Period from 2011 - 2023

Year	Value Production	Money Production	Capital Adequacy Ratio	Profitability Ratio	Credit Risk Ratio	Liquidity Ratio	Organization	Planned Net Income	Financial Intelligence
2011	0.52	0.05	0.37	0.02	0.11	0.52	0.37	0.04	0.83
2012	0.22	0.06	0.55	0.02	0.12	0.62	0.33	0.04	0.48
2013	0.46	0.08	0.59	0.02	0.08	0.57	0.3	0.08	0.89
2014	0.2	0.07	0.58	0.02	0.07	0.54	0.14	0.11	0.39
2015	0.05	0.02	0.64	0.004	0.11	0.69	0.18	0.08	0.11
2016	-0.11	0.05	0.86	0.02	0.13	0.68	0.25	0.1	-0.13

² Iraqi dinar symbol (official currency used in Iraq)

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2017	-0.24	0.01	1.03	0.006	0.18	0.69	0.35	0.06	-0.51
2018	-0.4	0.01	1.27	0.004	0.19	0.71	0.38	0.08	-1.03
2019	-0.41	0.02	0.64	0.006	0.21	0.61	0.5	0.08	-0.8
2020	-0.36	0.05	0.28	0.01	0.3	0.73	0.22	0.08	-0.51
2021	-0.11	0.07	0.34	0.02	0.36	0.58	0.22	0.08	-0.05
2022	-0.01	0.13	0.52	0.03	0.48	0.5	0.66	0.08	0.26
2023	1.19	0.38	0.67	0.06	0.65	0.71	0.3	0.08	3.88

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Bank of Baghdad (BBOB)

It is noted from the table above that the level of financial intelligence was fluctuating and positive during the period (2011-2015), but it shifted to a negative state throughout the period (2016-2021). This is due to the decline in financial intelligence. This fluctuation is due to the deterioration of the country's security and political situation, the war with the terrorist organization ISIS, and the terrorist organization's occupation of parts of Iraq's governorates, which affected the bank's branches. The branches (Al-Rabi', Tikrit, Ramadi, and Fallujah) were closed in 2016. As part of its 2016 plan, the Bank of Baghdad began implementing a restructuring plan to redistribute and expand its branches in line with economic changes and competitive conditions in the banking market. The year 2017 witnessed the merger of some branches, and the repercussions of this crisis continued on the bank until 2018, followed by the global Corona pandemic crisis, which negatively impacted the bank and its operations. It returned to positive territory for the next two years, settling at 3.88 in 2023, its highest level. This year's increase indicates that the

market value added ratio was high, reaching 1.19. This means that the bank succeeded in creating good value for investors, meaning that the bank achieved profits exceeding its invested capital, thus increasing its market value added. It also witnessed an increase in net profit and profitability, which, in turn, increased credit risk due to the bank's increased liquidity. While its lowest level was in 2018, reaching -1.03 during the study period, this decline in the financial intelligence ratio can be explained by the significant decline in market capitalization (0.40). Furthermore, there was a decline in net profit, which led to a decline in investor confidence in the bank, contributing to a decline in its market value. This was in addition to a decline in profitability and credit risk, unlike the liquidity ratio, which increased significantly despite the decline in credit risk. All of these factors contributed to a decline in the bank's financial intelligence. And figure below shows indicators of financial intelligence.

Figure 2. Illustration Financial Intelligence Indicators of Bank of Baghdad for Period from 2011 – 2023

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Bank of Baghdad (BBOB)

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3.4. Financial Performance Efficiency Indicators:- We will calculate Financial performance indicators with a focus on performance efficiency by using table as follows:

Table4. Illustration Financial Performance Indicators with a Focus on Performance Efficiency

Financial Performance	
Item	Equation
Profitability Index	Return on Equity Ratio = (Net Profit After Tax) / (Equity) x 100
Liquidity Index	Deposits to Investments Ratio = Investments / Deposits x 100
Safety Index	Equity to Total Deposits Ratio = (Equity / Total Deposits)
³Efficiency	Total Revenue / Total Expenses

Source: Prepared by researchers based on literature, including (ASADI, 2021)

Table5. Illustration Financial Performance Indicators with a Focus on Performance Efficiency of Bank of Baghdad for Period from 2011 - 2023

Year	Profitability Index	Liquidity Index	Safety Index	Efficiency
	Return on Equity Ratio	Ratio of Investments to Total Deposits	Ratio of Equity to Total Deposits	-----
2011	0.15	0.27	0.2	1.81
2012	0.12	0.23	0.2	1.90
2013	0.11	0.29	0.21	1.84
2014	0.1	0.31	0.2	1.76
2015	0.02	0.01	0.3	1.21
2016	0.07	0.01	0.34	1.57
2017	0.02	0.13	0.36	1.22
2018	0.01	0.12	0.34	1.17
2019	0.03	0.13	0.34	1.37
2020	0.07	0.16	0.26	1.74
2021	0.09	0.38	0.27	1.81
2022	0.15	0.51	0.27	2.32
2023	0.33	0.29	0.22	4.48

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Bank of Baghdad (BBOB)

From table above shows that profitability index was relatively close in 2011, gradually declining over the period (2012-2018). This was due to the decline in net income to its lowest level as a result of the circumstances facing the Iraqi economy in 2018, as well as the decline in revenues from net foreign exchange profits due to the bank's impact on the declining exchange rate in the Iraqi market. **Efficiency** levels were

relatively close, except for the final year, when it rose in 2012 and continued to fluctuate throughout the period (2013-2017), stabilizing in 2023, and its highest level during the study period. This was a result of the growth in total revenues and the decline in the bank's operating expenses, as total revenues reached their highest level during the study period in that year.

³ (ASADI, 2021).

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Figure3. Illustration Financial Performance Indicators with a Focus on Performance Efficiency of Bank of Baghdad for Period from 2011 - 2023

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Bank of Baghdad (BBOB)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive data analysis: - Now we will analyse the relationship between financial intelligence and the financial performance Efficiency of the Bank of Baghdad for the period (2011-2023). Through table as follows:

Table 6. Illustration Analysis of Relationship between Financial Intelligence and Financial Performance with a focus on Efficiency for Bank of Baghdad for period (2011-2023)

Year	Financial Intelligence	Profitability Index	Liquidity Index	Safety Index	Efficiency
2011	0.83	0.15	0.27	0.20	1.81
2012	0.48	0.12	0.23	0.20	1.90
2013	0.89	0.11	0.29	0.21	1.84
2014	0.39	0.1	0.31	0.2	1.76
2015	0.11	0.02	0.01	0.3	1.21
2016	-0.13	0.07	0.01	0.34	1.57
2017	-0.51	0.02	0.13	0.36	1.22
2018	-1.03	0.01	0.12	0.34	1.17
2019	-0.8	0.03	0.13	0.34	1.37
2020	-0.51	0.07	0.16	0.26	1.74
2021	-0.05	0.09	0.38	0.27	1.81
2022	0.26	0.15	0.51	0.27	2.32
2023	3.88	0.33	0.29	0.22	4.48
Total	3.81	1.27	2.84	3.51	24.2
Average	0.29	0.1	0.22	0.27	1.86
MAX	3.88	0.33	0.51	0.36	4.48
MIN	-1.03	0.01	0.01	0.20	1.17
⁴ CAGR	0.14	0.07	0.006	0.008	0.08
S.D	1.23	0.08	0.14	0.06	0.85

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Bank of Baghdad (BBOB)

⁴ It represents the compound annual growth rate and is calculated using the formula as follows: $CAGR = ((\frac{EV}{BV})^{1/n} - 1)$. (Fernando, 2024)

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From table above shows that financial intelligence and financial performance indicators of Bank of Baghdad have witnessed relative fluctuations between rise and fall throughout study period. When the financial intelligence decreased in 2012, which was reflected in profitability index represented by the return on equity ratio, as it decreased to 0.12, there was also a decrease in the liquidity index represented by the ratio of investments to total deposits at 0.23, while it was met with an increase in efficiency at 1.90. As for the safety index represented by the ratio of equity to deposits, it remained stable at the same amount from the previous year. During the period (2013-2014), the profitability index continued to gradually decline, as did efficiency. We also note that during this period, both the financial intelligence index and the safety index rose in 2013, and then declined in 2014. Liquidity index witnessed a gradual increase during this period. However, in 2015, financial intelligence, profitability index, liquidity, and efficiency index declined, while the safety index rose to 0.30. Then, during the period (2016-2021), financial intelligence continued to decline at a negative level, while financial performance indicators fluctuated between highs and lows during this period. During this period, the safety index reached its highest level at 0.36 in 2017, while the profitability index, liquidity index, and efficiency index reached their lowest levels during this period. Financial intelligence returned to the rise in 2022, along with the profitability, liquidity, and efficiency indexes. The liquidity

index reached its highest level throughout the study period at 0.51, while the safety index remained stable as in the previous year. Financial intelligence stabilized at its highest level in 2023 at 3.88. The profitability index also reached its highest level during this year, at 0.33, and the efficiency index reached 4.48, while the liquidity and safety indexes declined during the year. The total financial intelligence was 3.81, the profitability index was 1.27, the liquidity index was 2.84, the safety index was 3.51, and the efficiency total was 24.2, which is the highest total among its levels. Efficiency also achieved the highest average among them, reaching 1.86, followed by the average financial intelligence at 0.29, followed by the average safety index, which reached 0.27, then the average liquidity index, which reached 0.22, then the profitability index at 0.10. Financial intelligence, profitability index, and efficiency achieved their lowest levels in 2018. It is noted from Table 6 that compound growth rate (CAGR) had the highest level for financial intelligence at 0.14, followed by efficiency at 0.08, then the profitability index at 0.07, then the safety index at 0.008, then the liquidity index, which reached 0.006. Financial intelligence also achieved the highest standard deviation at 1.23, followed by efficiency at 0.85, then liquidity index at 0.14, then profitability index at 0.08, followed by safety index at 0.06. It is evident that there is a relatively direct relationship between financial intelligence and the financial performance indicators of Bank of Baghdad, despite continuous fluctuations during the study period. This is shown in figure as follows:

Figure4. Illustration Analysis of Relationship between Financial Intelligence and Financial Performance with a focus on Efficiency for Bank of Baghdad for period (2011-2023)

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Bank of Baghdad (BBOB)

5. CONCLUSION

- Financial intelligence enhances the efficiency of the Bank of Baghdad's financial performance. This was achieved in 2023, as the financial intelligence ratio reached **3.88** this positively impacted the financial performance efficiency index for 2023, reaching **4.48**, This proves the validity of the hypothesis that

financial intelligence enhances performance efficiency.

- Financial intelligence is used as an advanced method for analysing data and making appropriate strategic decisions in the short and long term.
- The decline in Financial Intelligence Index has contributed to a decline in the efficiency of the Bank

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of Baghdad's financial performance. This decline was evident in 2018, when the FII reached **(-1.03)** this negatively impacted the FII for 2023, which reached **1.17**; this proves that there is a direct relationship between financial intelligence and financial performance efficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

In this regard, we thank the management and employees of the Bank of Baghdad for helping us by providing us with the bank's final accounts and all the data we needed throughout the research period.

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